

Self-Compassion and Emotional Intelligence Among Working and Non- Working Women

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Abstract

The present study is an attempt to study Emotional Intelligence and Self- Compassion among working and non-working women. In this study, some qualitative analysis was done on the sample by asking them to fill up the questionnaires of Emotional Intelligence and Self-Compassion. The sample consisted of 15 working women and 15 non working women. Statistical method applied on the data was t-test along with analysis of correlation. Emotional Intelligence Scale is developed by Anukool Hyde, Sanjyot Pethe and Upinder Dhar and Self-Compassion scale developed by Kristin Moff. There is a significant difference between working and non working women on both Emotional Intelligence and Self-Compassion which shows that Working women are more self-compassionate and high in emotional intelligence. Non-working women due to limited social contact and not being able to experience financial independence makes them more critical about themselves in some cases which adversely affects their emotional intelligence.

Keywords - emotional intelligence, self-compassion, working women, non- working women

Self-Compassion

Compassion towards oneself has been a chief characteristic of individuals. The three components of self-compassion also broadens the horizon of this concept as it all comes to judgment free approach towards one's own and getting through grím moments of life. Kristin Neff, Ph.D. is a pioneer in the study of self compassion, being the first one to operationally define and measure the construct almost twenty years ago. She has been recognized as one of the world's most influential research psychologists. Kristin Neff has defined self-compassion as being composed of three main elements-self-kindness, common humanity, and mindfulness.

- **Self-kindness:** Self-compassion entails being warm towards oneself when encountering pain and personal shortcomings, rather than ignoring them or hurting oneself with self-criticism.
- **Common humanity:** Self-compassion also involves recognizing that suffering and personal failure is part of the shared human experience rather than isolating.
- **Mindfulness:** Self-compassion requires taking a balanced approach to one's negative emotions so that feelings are neither suppressed nor exaggerated. Negative thoughts and emotions are observed with openness, so that they are held in mindful awareness.

Self-compassion is simply the process of turning compassion inward. We are kind and understanding rather than harshly self-critical when we fail, make mistakes or feel inadequate. We give ourselves support and

encouragement rather than being cold and judgmental when challenges and difficulty arise in our lives. Research indicates that self-compassion is one of the most powerful sources of coping and resilience we have available to us, radically improving our mental and physical wellbeing.

Emotional Intelligence

Emotional intelligence is the area of cognitive ability that facilitates interpersonal behavior. The term emotional intelligence was popularized in 1995 by psychologist and behavioral science journalist Dr. Daniel Goleman in his book, *Emotional Intelligence*. Dr. Goleman described emotional intelligence as a person's ability to manage his feelings so that those feelings are expressed appropriately and effectively.

Cooper and Sawaf (1997) defines emotional intelligence as an ability that helps the individual to sense, understand and effectively apply the power and acumen of emotions as a source of human energy, information, connection and influence.

Dr. Goleman described emotional intelligence as a person's ability to manage his feelings so that those feelings are expressed appropriately and effectively. According to Goleman, emotional intelligence is the largest single predictor of success in the workplace.

Rational of Study

The aim of this study is to investigate the relationship between self-compassion and emotional intelligence and compare these psychological variables in working and non-working women. Through this research work, researchers tried understanding the level of self-compassion women have in working as well as non-working culture. Actual reason behind selecting this topic is to spread awareness about female's emotional health and explore more in the field of positive psychology. This study can help in exploring the factors affecting emotional intelligence and self-compassion of working and non-working women. It can also help in measuring the relationship between these psychological variables by considering the role of different lifestyles.

Objective

1. To compare working women and non working women on self compassion.
2. To compare working and non working women on emotional intelligence.
3. To study the relationship between self compassion and emotional intelligence among working women.
4. To study the relationship between self-compassion and emotional intelligence among non-working women.

Hypotheses

1. There is a significant difference among working and non-working women on the self- compassion scale.
2. There is a significant difference among working and non-working women on emotional intelligence scale.
3. There is a relationship between self compassion and emotional intelligence of working women.
4. There is a relationship between self compassion and emotional intelligence of non-working women. A

Method

Participants

A sample of 15 working and 15 non-working women was selected for the study between the age group of 20-35 years. The data of working and non-working women was collected from the general public.

Instruments-

- Self-compassion scale by Kristin Neff
- Emotional Intelligence Scale by Anukool Hyde, Sanjyot Pethe and Upinder Dhar

Statistical analysis

The data collected through Emotional intelligence scale and self-compassion scale have been assessed by using t-test which will give information about significant difference and Pearson product movement correlation have been used for measuring the relationship between emotional intelligence and self-compassion.

TABLE 1 Showing t-test among working and non-working women on self-compassion scale.

	mean	T value	df
Working women	3.96	10.8	28
Non-working women	3.09		

SIGNIFICANCE OF LEVEL 0.01 = 2.76

0.05 = 2.05

INFERENCE: t-value is significant at 28 df on 0.05 and 0.01 level

TABLE 2 Showing t-test among working and non-working women on emotional intelligence

	mean	T value	df
Working women	137.66	3.59	28
Non-working women	131		

SIGNIFICANCE OF LEVEL 0.01 = 2.76

0.05 = 2.05

INFERENCE: t value is significant at 28 df on 0.05 and 0.01 level.

TABLE 3 Showing correlation of emotional intelligence and self compassion among working women by using Pearson's r Product Movement

	R ratio	Correlation	level
Working women	0.54	positive	Moderate

INFERENCE: There is a positively moderate correlation between self-compassion and emotional intelligence among working women.

TABLE 4 Showing correlation of emotional intelligence and self-compassion among non- working women by using Pearson's Product Movement

	R ratio	correlation	Level
Non-working women	0.08	positive	Negligible coorelation

INFERENCE-There is a negligible correlation between self-compassion and emotional intelligence among non-working women.

Discussion

The purpose of the study is to compare emotional intelligence and self- compassion of working and nonworking women. Emotional Intelligence represents the ability to perceive, appraise and express emotion accurately and adaptively, the ability to understand emotion and emotional knowledge and the ability to regulate emotions in oneself and others (Mayer & Salovey 1997). Emotional intelligence is the construct responsible for a healthy life approach. Emotions influence perception, cognition, motivation, behavior, motor expression, subject feeling and decisions.

Self-compassion is defined as the acceptance one has for the quirks of one's own self and non-judgmental approach about self. Self-compassion plays a crucial role in forming self-image. It influences the self-esteem of the person and develops the outlook about oneself. Depending on the lifestyle of women they have varied emotional range and several studies were conducted to establish proper understanding about emotions.

The first research question was to find if there is any significant difference between working and non-working on a self-compassion scale. So a t-test was applied to find the significant difference. Obtained value of t was 10.875; df is 28 whereas table value at 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance was 2.76 and 2.05. As the obtained value was greater than the table value, the difference was found to be significant. Thus, the study shows there is a significant difference in self- compassion between working and non-working females.

Then the second research question was to find if there is any significant difference between working and non-working on Emotional Intelligence scale. So a t-test was applied to find the significant difference. Obtained value of t was 3.59; df is 28 whereas table value at 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance was 2.76 and 2.05. As the obtained value was greater than the table value, the difference was found to be significant. Thus, the study shows there is significant difference in emotional intelligence between working and non-working females.

The third research question focused on finding the relationship between self- compassion and emotional intelligence of working women. Correlation r was calculated to find the correlation between emotional

intelligence and self-compassion of working women. The correlation value of r was found to be 0.54 and was interpreted as positive moderate correlation.

The fourth research question focused on finding the relationship between self-compassion and emotional intelligence of non-working women. Correlation r was calculated to find the correlation between emotional intelligence and self-compassion of non-working women. The correlation value of r was found to 0.08 and was interpreted as positive negligible correlation.

Conclusion

Thus, it can be concluded from the study that there is a significant difference between working and non-working women in emotional intelligence and self-compassion. There is positive high correlation among working women and positive negligible correlation among non-working women. Social factors play Important role in emotional regulation of women and kindness towards oneself is of utmost importance for both working and non-working women. Thus, it is very important to have a healthy social circle and a good self-care regime to yield the value of self-love and compassion each woman deserves

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